

1 ***How do we integrate community data from***
2 ***Wikidata and the fuzzy-sl Wikibase into a***
3 ***cultural heritage knowledge graph?***

4

5 Daria Stefan*^{1,2}, Florian Thiery*², Fiona Schenk^{3,2}

6

7 ¹ TU Wien – Vienna, Austria

8 ² Research Squirrel Engineers Network – Mainz/Vienna, Germany/Austria

9 ³ Johannes Gutenberg Universität Mainz – Mainz, Germany

10

11 * Corresponding author(s)

12 Correspondence: daria.stefan57@gmail.com; mail@fthiery.de

13 **ABSTRACT**

14 Community-curated Wikibase ecosystems, most notably Wikidata, FactGrid, and
15 wikibase.cloud instances such as fuzzy-sl, have become significant sources of
16 Cultural Heritage (CH) and archaeological data. In parallel, infrastructure initiatives
17 (e.g., NFDI4Objects) are building CIDOC-aligned knowledge graphs that demand
18 robust provenance, semantic interoperability, and reproducibility. This paper presents
19 a semi-automated workflow for integrating Wikibase data into infrastructure-scale
20 graphs, including entity selection, ontology design aligned with CIDOC CRM (with
21 CRMarchaeo, CRMsci, and CRMdig as needed), scripted RDF transformation, open
22 publication of code and data, versioned snapshot releases, and ingestion into the
23 NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph. The approach preserves Wikidata-style qualifiers
24 and references while yielding an event- and provenance-centric representation. Two
25 use cases demonstrate feasibility and limits. The Irish Holy Wells dataset
26 showcases richly reified statements (e.g., use, sources) mapped to CIDOC events.
27 The Campanian Ignimbrite findspots in fuzzy-sl focus on location-centric modelling
28 and interdisciplinarity, requiring E53 Place as baseline with CRMarchaeo/CRMsci
29 specialisation for stratigraphy, sampling, and analysis. We discuss challenges in
30 ontology alignment, granularity, explicit treatment of uncertainty (“fuzzy/wobbly”
31 data), and sustaining semi-automated pipelines amid evolving community schemas.
32 We argue for identifier discipline, machine-actionable provenance, and FAIR Digital
33 Objects for each release. The outcome is an interoperable, federated ecosystem,
34 spanning triplestores, Wikibases, and FDOs, in which community knowledge bases
35 become partners of infrastructure graphs.

36

37 **Keywords:** Wikibase, Wikidata, Linked Data, Ontology, Archaeology, Geosciences

Introduction

39 Community-driven repositories and knowledge bases – most prominently Wikidata,
 40 FactGrid, and Wikibase instances on wikibase.cloud such as fuzzy-sl – constitute
 41 substantial reservoirs of cultural heritage (CH) and archaeology-related data [1], [2].
 42 Curated by volunteers, citizen scientists, and independent researchers, these platforms
 43 frequently close gaps left by project-bound initiatives and enrich the broader research
 44 ecosystem with timely, fine-grained observations and links to heterogeneous sources. In
 45 parallel, large-scale infrastructure efforts (e.g., within the German National Research
 46 Data Infrastructure, NFDI [3]) are building knowledge-graph-based services for feeding
 47 the interdisciplinary federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem [4], [5] (Fig. 1), grounded in
 48 established semantic frameworks (RDF/OWL) and domain ontologies such as CIDOC
 49 CRM and its extensions. A key challenge – and opportunity – lies in integrating
 50 community-driven resources with these infrastructure graphs in a way that is
 51 methodologically sound, FAIR, and sustainable.

52

53 **Figure 1** - A distributed Knowledge Graph Scheme bringing together Linked Open
 54 Data and FAIR Digital Objects approaches. Florian Thierry & Andreas Noback, CC BY
 55 4.0, via Wikimedia Commons.

56 Within this landscape, Germany's NFDI4Objects consortium [6] acts as an
 57 interdisciplinary hub for archaeology and cultural heritage, spanning an exceptionally
 58 broad temporal and material scope. The NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph¹ already
 59 interlinks diverse datasets² (e.g., Linked Open Ogham, African Red Slip Ware, Linked
 60 Open Samian Ware), employing CIDOC CRM and selected extensions (e.g., CRMarchaeo,
 61 CRMdig) to enable interoperable querying across collections, sites, and research
 62 outputs³. Leveraging Linked Open Data (LOD) practices [7], [8] here is not merely a
 63 technical choice: it underpins reproducible scholarship, traceable provenance, and

¹ cf. <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/>

² cf. <https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/collection/>

³ cf. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13946052>

64 cross-dataset discovery. The question, then, is how to interface curated, evolving
65 community platforms – each with its own modelling idioms and governance – with a
66 harmonised, CIDOC-aligned knowledge graph at infrastructure scale.

67

68 Our proposed approach is a semi-automated, six-step workflow that (1) identifies
69 CH-relevant entities in Wikibase instances, (2) designs or selects an ontology aligned to
70 CIDOC CRM (supplemented where appropriate), (3) transforms the source data into RDF
71 via scripted pipelines, (4) publishes code and data for citation and versioning, (5)
72 releases regular dataset snapshots to ensure currency and persistence, and (6) ingests
73 these releases into, e.g. the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph. This pipeline aims to
74 respect the open-world assumption of LOD and preserve the rich context of statements
75 and qualifiers. It references typical Wikidata-style modelling, while producing a coherent,
76 event- and provenance-centric representation in CIDOC CRM.

77

78 The Wikiverse provides complementary affordances in this setting [9], [10]. Wikidata
79 offers multilingual breadth, mature property constraints, and widely adopted identifiers;
80 FactGrid supports humanities-oriented projects with detailed historical context; and
81 fuzzy-sl targets spatial uncertainty explicitly, introducing modelling patterns for
82 vagueness and ambiguity in findspot descriptions. By triangulating across these
83 strengths, we can derive a least common denominator of classes and properties that is
84 both mappable to CIDOC CRM and serviceable for downstream analytical tasks. The
85 objective is not to erase local nuances but to encode them faithfully, for example, by
86 transforming qualifiers and reifications into event-centred CIDOC constructs with explicit
87 timespans, actors, and sources.

88

89 Two use cases anchor our contribution. First, the Irish Holy Wells dataset (Wikidata's
90 WikiProject Holy Wells⁴) exemplifies richly reified statements that combine status,
91 conservation, and sourcing practices across heterogeneous evidence (e.g., Ordnance
92 Survey maps, local histories, Wikimedia Commons media). Here, the task is to preserve
93 referential integrity (Q/P identifiers) and transform qualifiers into CIDOC CRM event
94 patterns, thereby enabling temporal reasoning and provenance-aware queries. Second,
95 the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) findspots [11] from the fuzzy-sl Wikibase focus on spatial
96 uncertainty and cross-domain alignment (archaeology–geosciences). In this case,
97 fuzzy-sl categories and qualifiers can be mapped to CIDOC CRM (with
98 CRMsci/CRMarchaeo as needed), while preserving uncertainty envelopes and
99 observational provenance. Both cases stress machine-actionable provenance and
100 interoperable uncertainty, which are prerequisites for meaningful aggregation across
101 NFDI4Objects and beyond. Methodologically, three principles guide the integration:

102

103 1. **Identifier discipline.** We retain or reference authoritative URIs (e.g., Wikidata
104 Q-codes) and, where appropriate, assert equivalences (e.g., owl:sameAs) to
105 maintain global coherence. This minimises fragile string-matching and ensures
106 stable joins across sources.

107

⁴ cf. https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_HolyWells

108 2. **Event-centric modelling.** Rather than collapsing complex, qualified statements
109 into timeless triples, we materialise the implied activities (assessment,
110 documentation, naming, celebration, sampling) as CIDOC CRM events with
111 agents, timespans, and documentary evidence. This preserves semantics
112 essential for historical reasoning and data quality assessment.

113

114 3. **Uncertainty as first-class data.** Spatial vagueness, competing attributions, and
115 evolving states are modelled explicitly (e.g., via condition assessments and
116 temporally scoped states; fuzzy spatial footprints), aligning with the open-world
117 assumption and avoiding misleading false precision.

118

119 In sum, we position community knowledge bases not as external “feeds” but as
120 coequal knowledge partners whose specificity and dynamism enrich infrastructure-scale
121 graphs. By combining scripted workflows, CIDOC-compliant patterns, and rigorous
122 identifier strategies, our approach enhances the FAIRness and analytic utility of CH data
123 while maintaining the flexibility for periodic, automated refreshes that keep
124 infrastructure graphs in sync with ongoing community efforts. In this way, Wikibase
125 instances can become integral parts of an interdisciplinary federated Knowledge Graph
126 ecosystem that spans triplestores, Wikibases, and FAIR Digital Objects.

127

Use Case: Irish Holy Wells from Wikidata

128 The WikiProject HolyWells (Q126443484) provides a complex and richly structured
129 dataset. It combines contributions from both academic researchers and citizen
130 scientists, complements textual data [12] with richly annotated media from Wikimedia
131 Commons, and integrates information from heterogeneous sources, both digital and
132 analogue (Fig. 2 and 3). By using reifications, the project documents the evolution of
133 conservation and use status, specifying the context in which each condition was
134 recorded. These features are optimal for demonstrating the process of aligning a flexible
135 model like Wikidata to an interoperable and consistent semantic framework like CIDOC
136 CRM, while also exposing the practical challenges that arise when attempting to
137 automate the transformation of such multifaceted data.

138

139

Figure 2 - Example: The Citizen Science Wikidata Project Holy Wells. CC0.

140

141

Figure 3 - Freshford: St Lachtain's Well in Wikidata. CC0 and OSM Contributors.

142 This project aims to develop a semi-automatic ontology design and alignment
 143 workflow that can be implemented entirely with Python libraries. The current workflow
 144 prototype begins by querying Wikidata and storing the data in relational tables within
 145 Postgres. A CIDOC CRM compliant ontology is designed in Protégé, along with
 146 mappings that associate the data stored in Postgres with its new form. Then the triples
 147 are materialised using the Ontop plugin, creating the final knowledge graph. While the
 148 extraction, transformation, and loading processes can be largely automated using
 149 Python libraries, designing a CIDOC CRM-compliant ontology remains a non-trivial task,
 150 as it requires careful analysis and alignment of the loosely structured information from
 151 Wikidata. In the following sections, we outline how the data was acquired, structured,
 152 and ultimately aligned with CIDOC CRM, as well as the specific challenges we
 153 encountered.

154

155 Querying Wikidata

156

157 For the data exploration step, we set up a SPARQL endpoint and queried for all triples
158 with an instance of Holy Well Semantic Concept (Q126443332) as their subject. Holy
159 Well Semantic Concept is a subclass of Holy Well (Q1371047), and every entry in the
160 Irish Holy Wells project is an instance of this class.

161

162 To ensure both accuracy and interoperability, queries retrieve not only the
163 human-readable labels for entities and properties but also their unique Wikidata
164 identifiers: Q-IDs for entities and P-IDs for properties. Embedding these Q-IDs directly
165 into the URLs of individuals modelled in Protégé while keeping the Wikidata prefix is our
166 strategy for maintaining referential integrity. Human-readable labels, descriptions, and
167 aliases are still incorporated as `rdfs:label`, `skos:altLabel`, and `schema:description`,
168 allowing semantic clarity for human users and multilingual applications.

169

170 The initial query retrieved 229 distinct subjects and 37 unique statements. Among the
171 most frequently used properties are 'described by source' (P1343), 'instance of' (P31),
172 'located in the administrative territorial entity' (P131), 'inventory number' (P217), and
173 'collection' (P195). Wikidata's data model is built around statements, qualifiers, and
174 references [13]. Each fact is expressed as a statement, while qualifiers add contextual
175 conditions and references point to supporting evidence, but are not directly connected to
176 the subject. All statements were examined for their domain and range constraints to
177 facilitate semantic alignment and to ensure accurate mapping into a CIDOC CRM-based
178 ontology.

179

180 For some entries, both status information and contextual information are missing
181 altogether; for others, statuses are declared directly as properties, without further
182 supporting information. A smaller subset contains reified statements, which allow
183 qualifiers such as the state of use to be attached to a property, such as 'instance of'
184 (P31) and for references to be added as well, mentioning the source of the claim. Both
185 the classification of the entity and an assessment of its condition are linked to the same
186 piece of evidence. From a CIDOC CRM perspective, this practice aligns with the
187 event-centric modelling of knowledge, where the assertion of a property is itself situated
188 in time, attributed to an actor, and supported by evidence. Queries over such statements
189 aim to preserve their structure and context, retrieving not only the complete statement,
190 but also the superclass of the source and all additional information contained on the
191 source's page, such as author and publication date.

192

193 Wikidata incorporates and references external resources such as YouTube,
194 OpenStreetMap, Irish Sites and Monuments Records through specific properties known
195 as external identifiers. Those properties are all instances of subclasses of the class
196 Unique Identifier (Q6545185). For each identifier, queries collect both the reference itself
197 and its associated qualifiers, which may include retrieval date, publisher, or language,
198 and in some cases, the classification of the qualifier values. For example, a linked
199 'YouTube video' (P1651) can be queried alongside the video's 'publication date' (P577)

200 and 'duration' (P2047), showing how audiovisual content is anchored in Wikidata with
201 descriptive and temporal attributes.

202

203 A different strategy is required for Wikimedia Commons, since metadata such as
204 authorship, credit, and licensing is not fully exposed through the Wikidata SPARQL
205 endpoint. Instead, filenames retrieved from Wikidata must first be normalised, after
206 which the Wikimedia API is used to fetch extended metadata. HTML fragments are then
207 parsed to extract structured information, such as artist, credit name and links. While the
208 technical querying mechanism differs, the goal remains the same—enriching identifiers
209 with contextual metadata, like date and place of the creation of an image, its author and
210 license policy.

211

212 Alongside reified statements and external identifiers, some properties are expressed
213 as direct statements without additional qualifiers. These include spatial and categorical
214 attributes such as geographic coordinates (converted into both WKT and DMS formats
215 for standardised representation), diocese affiliation, and medical condition. For these
216 cases, a simplified query pattern retrieves the subject–predicate–object triple directly
217 and supplements it with the 'instance of' (P31) classification of the object, ensuring that
218 even simple statements remain embedded within a structured and interpretable data
219 model.

220

221 **CIDOC CRM Ontology Mapping**

222

223 Translating the acquired information into CIDOC CRM requires the construction of a
224 custom ontology with mappings. While the ultimate aim is to develop a semi-automated
225 workflow, we currently produce them manually, providing a valuable "ground truth" for
226 future experiments with automation. The procedure begins with identifying salient
227 features of both ontologies: for Wikidata, these include entity Q-codes, labels,
228 descriptions, 'instance of' (P31) values, and property domain and range restrictions,
229 while for CIDOC CRM they consist of class descriptions and property domain and range
230 constraints as defined in the documentation. The representative example of
231 Columbkile's Well (Q126456441) was modelled according to Table 1:

232
233

Table 1 – correspondences when modelling relationship instance of (P31) in wikidata to a CIDOC compliant ontology for the example entity Columbkille’s well.

Columbkille’s Well			
Wikidata		Ontology	
Well is Instance Of X	X is Subclass Of	Well is Instance Of Y	Y is Subclass of
Archaeological site (Q839954)	location of discovery (Q1291195), human-geographic territorial entity (Q15642541), geographic location (Q2221906)	Archaeological Site	<i>E27 Site, E53 Place</i>
Water source (Q10713454)	body of water (Q15324), water resource (Q1049799)	Water Source	<i>E27 Site, E53 Place</i>
Holy well (Q1371047)	fountain(Q483453), structure of worship(Q1370598) spring (Q124714), water well(Q43483)	Holy Well	Fountain, Water Well (both are subclasses of <i>E25 Human made Feature</i>)
Holy well semantic concept (Q126443332)	Holy well (Q1371047)	Holy Well Semantic Concept	Holy Well

234

235 This step brings in another level of complexity: the relationships from Wikidata do not
236 correspond one-to-one to the ones defined in CIDOC, since the latter is event-based, and
237 most events, like documenting, assessing, naming, or celebrating, are not explicitly
238 stated in Wikidata. The implied existence of these events has to be recognised by a
239 human and placed in the correct context, modelling causality and temporality.

240

241 Once the relevant classes have been identified, the relationships between their
242 instances must also be translated. This can be automated through the use of
243 mappings—queries that extract data from the relational database created after querying
244 Wikidata and reshape it into the target ontology structure, thereby materialising
245 individuals. Although Ontop automates the materialisation step itself, the mappings that
246 define how the data is transformed (Figure 10) need to be written manually.

247

248 The following cases illustrate this modelling process using Columbkille’s well as an
249 example. For the ‘named after’ property (P138), the process begins by retrieving the
250 subject (Columbkille’s Well), predicate and object (Columba), together with the object’s
251 Q-code (Q236326), class (human) and labels from Wikidata. A corresponding individual
252 (Columba) is created in the ontology, as an instance of the correct CIDOC class, *E21*
253 *Person*. Columbkille’s Well is identified by its name, which is a new individual instance of
254 *E41 Appellation*. This name ‘*P67 refers to*’ Columba, the person.

255

256 The feast day celebration of Columba was ‘*P17 motivated by*’ Columba and ‘*P4 has*
257 *timespan*’ of the Feast Day of Columba, a new individual instance of *E7 Activity*. June 9 is
258 a new individual instance of *SP14 Time Expression* and ‘*Q16 defines time*’ for the feast
259 day without modifying the string returned by the wikidata query.

260

261 The wikidata property 'feast day' (P841) is constrained to values that are instances of
 262 a point in time with respect to recurrent timeframe (Q14795564). To maintain this
 263 information about June 9, the recurrence of the feast day is currently also noted (*P3 has*
 264 *note*) using an iCalendar RRULE expression
 265 (FREQ=YEARLY;BYMONTH=6;BYMONTHDAY=9). The current model of this section of the
 266 knowledge graph is shown in Figure 4.

267

268 **Figure 4** - The 'named after' property and the 'feast day' property modelled in the
 269 CIDOC CRM compliant ontology. Daria Stefan, CC BY 4.0.

270

271 Additionally, owl:Time can be used, enabling SPARQL Queries to find events that
 272 happen on June 9th, as shown in Figure 5. True recurrence would imply generating
 273 individual instances for each year, which would enable reasoning, but clog the
 274 knowledge graph.

275

276

277 **Figure 5** - The recurrence of the feast day modelled using owl:Time and the SP14
 278 Time Expression class. Daria Stefan, CC BY 4.0.

279 A second important modeling strategy concerns the treatment of reified statements.
 280 In Wikidata, they are represented through qualifiers and references attached to a primary
 281 subject-object link. For example, the property 'instance of' (P31) between Toberbride
 282 (Q122258940) and Holy Well (Q1371047) may include the state of use as a qualifier and
 283 the source as a reference. In CIDOC CRM, reifications are expressed in an event-based
 284 manner. The assignment of Toberbride to the category "Holy Well" constitutes one event
 285 (Figure 6), while a condition assessment constitutes another (Figure 7), with multiple
 286 events potentially documented by the same source.

287

288 In CIDOC, Each *E14 Condition Assessment* node represents the act of evaluating the
 289 condition of a holy well. This is not as a simple binary link, but an n-ary relationship that
 290 connects the assessed well, the assigned state, and the documenting source. Using '*P2*
 291 *has type*', we distinguish what sort of assessment was made, whether it concerns use or
 292 preservation state. This allows a well to hold multiple, non-exclusive state assignments.

293

294 Each *E17 Type Assignment* event in CIDOC represents the documented classification
 295 of an individual as a holy well from Wikidata. If this assignment is not stated as a
 296 reification with a source, *P2* can be used. In Figure 7, the assignment to Holy Well is
 297 documented, but the assignment to Holy Well Semantic Concept is direct. By modelling
 298 states as individuals, we preserve flexibility in defining possible states while remaining
 299 consistent with Wikidata's original structure.

300

301
302
303

Figure 6 - Type assignment modelled in the CIDOC CRM compliant ontology. Daria Stefan, CC BY 4.0.

304
305
306

Figure 7 - Use and conservation state reifications modelled in the CIDOC CRM compliant ontology. Daria Stefan, CC BY 4.0.

307 To further contextualize these assessments, the publication date of each source was
308 also queried and integrated into the model as a *E65 Creation Event* (Figure 8). This
309 approach ensures that the state of a well is not presented as a static or universal fact
310 but as the outcome of a particular assessment, carried out by a specific actor at a
311 defined moment in time.
312

313

314 **Figure 8** - Creation event. Daria Stefan, CC BY 4.0.

315 Finally, for 'collection' (P195) and 'inventory number' (P217), an *E15 Identifier*
 316 *Assignment Event* is instantiated for each holy well indexed in a collection. It connects an
 317 inventory number to the holy well (*P140 assigned attribute to*) and the specific collection
 318 in which the well is indexed (*P16 used specific object*). If an individual is directly
 319 'described by source' (P1343), a direct 'P70 documents' connection is added (Figure 9).

320

321 **Figure 9** - Inventory number, collection, direct documentation. Daria Stefan, CC BY
 322 4.0.

<p>Create and classify assignment event</p> <pre> :E15_Identifier_Assignment_Event_{subject_q}_{inventory_id}_{collection_q} a cidoc-crm:E15_Identifier_Assignment . SELECT inventory_id, subject_q, collection_q FROM inventory_id_coll WHERE inventory_id IS NOT NULL; </pre>
<p>P16 used specific object</p> <pre> :E15_Identifier_Assignment_Event_{subject_q}_{inventory_id}_{collection_q} cidoc-crm:P16_used_specific_object wdQ:{collection_q} . SELECT inventory_id, subject_q, collection_q FROM inventory_id_coll WHERE inventory_id IS NOT NULL; </pre>
<p>P37 assigned</p> <pre> :E15_Identifier_Assignment_Event_{subject_q}_{inventory_id}_{collection_q} cidoc-crm:P37_assigned :inventory_number_{subject_q}_{inventory_id}_{collection_q} . SELECT inventory_id, subject_q, collection_q FROM inventory_id_coll WHERE inventory_id IS NOT NULL; </pre>
<p>Create and classify inventory number</p> <pre> :inventory_number_{subject_q}_{inventory_id}_{collection_q} a cidoc-crm:E42_Identifier . SELECT inventory_id, subject_q, collection_q FROM inventory_id_coll WHERE inventory_id IS NOT NULL; </pre>
<p>P140 assigned attribute to</p> <pre> :E15_Identifier_Assignment_Event_{subject_q}_{inventory_id}_{collection_q} cidoc-crm:P140_assigned_attribute_to wdQ:{subject_q} . SELECT inventory_id, subject_q, collection_q FROM inventory_id_coll WHERE inventory_id IS NOT NULL; </pre>
<p>P177 assigned property of type</p> <pre> :E15_Identifier_Assignment_Event_{subject_q}_{inventory_id}_{collection_q} cidoc-crm:P177_assigned_property_of_type :E42_Identifier . :E42_Identifier a SELECT inventory_id, subject_q, collection_q FROM inventory_id_coll WHERE inventory_id IS NOT NULL; </pre>
<p>P70 documents</p> <pre> wdQ:{object_q} cidoc-crm:P70_documents wdQ:{subject_q} . SELECT subject_q, subject, object_q, object, instance_of_q, instance_of FROM described_by_source WHERE subject_q IS NOT NULL; </pre>

323

324 **Figure 10** -Ontop mappings for the elements of Figure 9. Daria Stefan, CC BY 4.0.

325 **Use Case: Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots from fuzzy-sl Wikibase**

326 The eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) around 39,940 yr b2k ± 150 [14]
327 represents one of the most significant volcanic events in Europe during the Late
328 Pleistocene, dispersing ash layers across vast areas of the continent. As a geological
329 phenomenon, the eruption is well documented in stratigraphy and tephrochronology, yet
330 its cultural significance emerges through its intersection with archaeological contexts.
331 Sites preserving CI deposits, whether geological outcrops or archaeological caves, thus
332 constitute a privileged case for examining how interdisciplinary data can be integrated
333 into a federated knowledge graph ecosystem.

334

335 In the fuzzy-sl Wikibase, CI-related entries⁵ are currently conceptualised as locations,
336 distinguished into two categories: Archaeological Sites (Q10⁶; e.g., caves or shelters with
337 evidence of human presence and CI deposits) and Geological Sites (Q11; outcrops,
338 cores, or tephra exposures identified through fieldwork). Both categories are
339 provisionally aligned as subclasses of *E53 Place* (Q146), following the CIDOC CRM
340 definition as “extents in the natural space where people live [...] independent from
341 temporal phenomena and matter.” This pragmatic modelling decision ensures
342 interoperability but raises the question of whether further granularity, e.g., introducing
343 subclasses or extending with CRMarchaeo and CRMsci, is required to capture
344 domain-specific nuances.

⁵ cf. <https://tinyurl.com/27buupzj>

⁶ cf. <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/entity/Q10>

345

346

347

348

349

350

Figure 11 - Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) sites created using the SPARQLing Unicorn Research Toolkit. A: CI sites categorised by type; B: Excerpt of the findspots near Naples; CD: Franchthi Cave as cisite_45 with archaeological findings and cave entrance. A/B/C: CC BY 4.0, Florian Thierly & Fiona Schenk; C images: CC BY-SA 4.0, Zde (artefacts); Xalaros, CC BY (cave).

351

352

353

Figure 12 - Franchthi Cave [Q111] in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase. Florian Thierly / Fiona Schenk, CC BY 4.0.

354 For archaeological sites, examples include Toplitsa Cave [15] (Q115), Franchthi Cave
355 [16] (Q111; Fig. 11 and 12), and Crvena Stijena Cave [17] (Q89). These locations are
356 relevant because they combine evidence of human occupation with CI tephra, allowing
357 for inferences about human – environment interactions, chronological anchors, and
358 cultural responses to volcanic events. Within a CIDOC CRM perspective, these entities
359 can remain modelled as *E53 Place*, but require linking to *E27 Site* (culturally defined
360 locale) and, where excavation data exist, to CRMarchaeo’s *A8 Stratigraphic Unit* for layers
361 containing volcanic ash. Events such as the deposition of tephra or its discovery can
362 then be represented as *E5 Event* instances, enabling temporal and causal reasoning.

363

364 For geological sites, entries such as DE3 Dehner Maar (Q85), Auel Maar AU3 (Q70),
365 and Urluia Quarry [18] (Q73) document CI deposits identified through field surveys and
366 geoscientific sampling [14]. Here, CIDOC CRM alone is insufficient. Integration with
367 CRMsci is necessary to represent sampling activities (e.g., S4 Observation, S19
368 Encounter Event) and analytical outcomes, while CRMdig can support provenance of
369 laboratory processes. This ensures that tephra samples are not merely attributes of
370 places but are documented as entities generated by scientific procedures with traceable
371 provenance and reproducibility.

372

373 At present, the fuzzy-sl Wikibase captures these sites primarily as labelled places
374 with coordinates and limited qualifiers. The properties and qualifiers are not yet mapped
375 to CIDOC CRM, reflecting the still-experimental state of the modelling. Nonetheless, this
376 dataset highlights a methodological challenge: how to align heterogeneous disciplinary
377 perspectives on the “same” site. Archaeologists prioritise cultural layers and human
378 interaction, whereas geoscientists focus on stratigraphic sequences and geochemical
379 signatures. A federated graph must accommodate both perspectives without flattening
380 them into an oversimplified schema. The interdisciplinary integration can be achieved by
381 adopting an event-centric approach:

382

- 383 ● The eruption itself is modelled as an *E5 Event*, producing deposits with a defined
384 timespan.
- 385 ● Geological observations (sampling, analysis) are modelled via CRMsci, linked to
386 both the deposits and the places where they occur.
- 387 ● Archaeological contexts are represented as *E27 Sites*, stratigraphic units, or
388 material culture associations, connected to the same deposits but with additional
389 cultural interpretation.

390

391 By interlinking these elements, the knowledge graph supports queries that traverse
392 disciplinary boundaries, e.g., “Which archaeological sites with CI deposits coincide with
393 geologically dated findspots older than ~40.000 yr b2k?” or “Which stratigraphic
394 contexts combine volcanic ash with artefactual assemblages?” Crucially, this case
395 demonstrates the role of CIDOC CRM as an interoperability bridge. While *E53 Place*
396 suffices as a baseline, interdisciplinary data integration requires layering additional
397 ontologies. For CI findspots, this means that the same URI may function simultaneously
398 as a *E53 Place*, an *E27 Archaeological Site*, and the locus of scientific observations

399 (CRMsci). Such polyhierarchical modelling aligns with the open-world assumption and
400 preserves the capacity to expand as new data or disciplinary perspectives emerge.

401

402 From the perspective of the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph, the CI case offers an
403 opportunity rather than a limitation. Even though the implementation is not yet
404 operational, the conceptual mapping illustrates how community-curated Wikibase data
405 can flow into infrastructure-scale graphs. The benefit lies in establishing identifier
406 discipline (stable URIs, equivalences to Wikidata Q-IDs), documenting provenance of
407 scientific activities, and ensuring that uncertainty in spatial and chronological resolution
408 is not collapsed but explicitly represented.

409

410 In conclusion, the Campanian Ignimbrite use case underscores the potential of
411 semi-automated workflows for federated knowledge graph construction. By integrating
412 fuzzy-sl data into a CIDOC-aligned graph, we not only capture a pivotal Late Pleistocene
413 volcanic event but also showcase how interdisciplinary collaboration – bridging geology
414 and archaeology – can be encoded as Linked Open Data. This sets the stage for future
415 implementation where lab analysis of CI sites becomes FAIR Digital Objects within the
416 broader federated ecosystem of NFDI and beyond.

417

Discussion & Conclusion & Outlook

418 The two case studies highlight both the opportunities and the challenges of
419 integrating community-curated Wikibase data into infrastructure-scale knowledge
420 graphs. The Holy Wells illustrate the potential of richly reified cultural heritage
421 statements, while the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) findspots expose the difficulties of
422 aligning archaeological and geoscientific perspectives.

423

424 A key challenge lies in ontology alignment and modelling. Wikibase properties and
425 qualifiers are often too flexible to be mapped directly into CIDOC CRM structures. While
426 CIDOC CRM provides an event-centric framework, its extensions (CRMarchaeo, CRMsci,
427 CRMdig) are required to represent stratigraphic reasoning, sampling procedures, and
428 laboratory provenance.

429

430 For the Holy Wells example, the first exploration step revealed a modelling
431 inconsistency in Wikidata: instances of Holy Well Semantic Concept appear as the
432 subjects of the 'feast day' (P841) property, despite it being restricted to humans, groups
433 of humans, titles of Mary, legendary figures, attributes of God, Bible stories, or
434 periscopes. Additionally, Holy Wells are not consistently named after or associated with
435 Christian religious concepts, nor do they always have a fixed feast day. For example, the
436 Well of the Rags (Q126647640) is named after a cloutie tree (Q107257053) and has a
437 feast day "Sunday after August 13". This issue also ties in with the conservation and
438 usage state qualifiers: according to the project description, if the feast day of a well is
439 currently being celebrated, it should be marked as being in use (Q55654238) and as an
440 instance of (P31) a religious site (Q105889895).

441

442 Although humans can intuitively understand these associations, modelling them in
443 CIDOC CRM raises questions: If the celebration is to be modelled as an event, then
444 additional contextual details are required: Is the celebration motivated by devotion to a
445 specific religious figure? Does it take place at the well itself, or does it involve the well in
446 any way? Has the celebration been documented, and if so, by whom and when? Was it
447 historically tied to a particular period, and is it still practised today? These questions
448 highlight which contextual information is not explicitly encoded and must therefore be
449 added when modelling the data in CIDOC, taking the feast day from a simple recurring
450 point in time to an ontologically appropriate entity that expresses the researchers'
451 intended semantic construct.

452

453 Additionally, the project suggests a simplified modelling strategy that limits state
454 qualifiers to two options (in use or abandoned), and conservation state qualifiers to
455 three (preserved, in danger, or demolished/destroyed), even though Wikidata property
456 constraints allow for a much wider range of values. This strategy implicitly reflects a
457 closed world assumption in which the qualifiers are treated as mutually exclusive and
458 exhaustive: if a well is not in use, it is assumed to be abandoned. LOD operates under an
459 open-world assumption, where the absence of a qualifier does not imply its negation; the
460 list of possible states is not seen as exhaustive, and states can co-occur. CIDOC CRM
461 aligns with the open world assumption and supports fine-grained modelling of use and
462 conservation states across time, while also drawing attention to the gaps that hinder
463 automatic reasoning.

464

465 Another challenge is posed by the classification step, where candidate
466 correspondences are generated by comparing the Wikidata classes against CIDOC
467 classes. This step proved challenging even for humans, as it requires a nuanced
468 understanding of the fine-grained distinctions in CIDOC CRM (e.g. *E22 Human-Made*
469 *Object* vs *E25 Human-Made Feature* or *E31 Document* vs *E73 Information Object*), the
470 implications of CIDOC's inheritance hierarchy for property domains and ranges, as well
471 as basic understanding of the modelled subjects and their individual particularities.
472 Deciding on an appropriate granularity level for the classification step is a further
473 non-trivial task: too generic, and valuable semantics are lost; too specific, and
474 interoperability suffers.

475

476 The decision-making process and heuristics employed to classify Columbkile's Well
477 (Q126456441, Table 1) were based mainly on "common sense" and background
478 knowledge, which is notoriously flimsy and difficult to encode into a formal decision
479 graph for computational use. If the process were to be automated, subsequent steps
480 would involve computing similarity measures for all candidate correspondences,
481 aggregating these results, and applying thresholds to filter out unreliable pairings. The
482 mapping would then be refined through iterative cycles, incorporating structural indices,
483 contextual neighbourhood information, map-discovery and map-repair techniques, until
484 consistency is reached and all classes find a correspondence. This process would be
485 applied not only to all 229 subjects in the Wikidata project but also to every entity
486 appearing as an object in a related statement, qualifier, or reference. The scale and

487 heterogeneity of this task make it clear that one of the central challenges lies in
488 developing an automated approach that is simultaneously scalable and reliable.

489

490 The second challenge is interdisciplinarity. Archaeologists tend to focus on cultural
491 layers, artefacts, and human activities, while geoscientists prioritise stratigraphy,
492 geochemistry, and analytical workflows. Modelling a single location as both an
493 archaeological site and a geological outcrop requires multi-perspective representations
494 that can coexist without contradiction.

495

496 The CI case shows that the same entity may need to function simultaneously as an
497 *E53 Place*, an *E27 Site*, and the locus of a CRMsci observation. Such polyhierarchical
498 modelling is conceptually demanding but essential if the federated graph is to support
499 queries across disciplines. A further issue is uncertainty. Community data often contains
500 vague coordinates, contested chronologies, or shifting attributions. Unless explicitly
501 represented, these ambiguities risk being flattened into misleading precision. Handling
502 “fuzzy” and “wobbly” data requires not only technical modelling patterns but also shared
503 standards that balance usability with accuracy. Automation and sustainability present
504 another layer of difficulty. Semi-automated pipelines (SPARQL extraction, RDF
505 conversion, ETL) are indispensable for scalability, yet they depend on evolving
506 community schemas. Quality assurance, persistent identifiers, and versioned releases
507 are needed to ensure that infrastructure knowledge graphs remain stable even as
508 community instances change dynamically.

509

510 In sum, the discussion reveals a tension between community dynamism and
511 infrastructure stability. Community Wikibases thrive on openness, rapid evolution, and
512 volunteer contributions; infrastructures such as NFDI4Objects require persistence,
513 citability, and reliability. Reconciling these modes demands careful governance,
514 reproducible workflows, and machine-actionable provenance.

515

516 Looking forward, the ontology used in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase will require refinement
517 and closer alignment with CIDOC CRM, MaChECo, and the Object Core Metadata Profile.
518 Semi-automated workflows for extraction and mapping must be stabilised, with each
519 release packaged as a FAIR Digital Object. More importantly, the development of
520 community standards for uncertainty and interdisciplinarity will be central to scaling
521 beyond individual use cases. If these steps are taken, Wikibase instances such as
522 Wikidata, FactGrid, and fuzzy-sl can evolve from experimental repositories into integral
523 components of a federated, interdisciplinary knowledge graph ecosystem that bridges
524 archaeology, cultural heritage, and the geosciences.

525

Acknowledgements

526 The authors would like to thank Stephen Stead for his advice as well as the CAA
527 Germany, SIG Data Dragon and NFDI4Objects Community. The authors acknowledge the
528 use of language assistance powered by artificial intelligence (ChatGPT, OpenAI) for
529 stylistic editing and linguistic refinement. All content and arguments were authored and
530 verified by the authors themselves.

531 Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

532 Distel, A.K. et al. (2025). Wikidata:WikiProject HolyWells:
533 https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:WikiProject_HolyWells ;
534 Thiery, F. et al. (2025). fuzzy-sl Wikibase: <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud>;
535 Thiery, F., & Schenk, F. (2023). Campanian Ignimbrite Geo Locations [DataSet] at
536 <https://github.com/Research-Squirrel-Engineers/campanian-ignimbrite-geo> [19];
537 Stefan, D. (2025). Holy Wells to CIDOC [Software] at
538 https://github.com/CopyKittyCode/Holy_Wells_to_CIDOC;

539 Conflict of interest disclosure

540 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts
541 of interest in relation to the content of the article.

542 Funding

543 The authors declare that they have received no specific funding for this study.

544 References

- 545 [1] L. Rossenova, P. Duchesne, and I. Blümel, 'Wikidata and Wikibase as complementary
546 research data management services for cultural heritage data', in *Proceedings of the*
547 *3rd Wikidata Workshop 2022 co-located with the 21st International Semantic Web*
548 *Conference (ISWC2022)*, 2022. [Online]. Available:
549 <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3262/paper15.pdf>
- 550 [2] F. Thiery, A. W. Mees, and J. B. Kiesling, 'Challenges in research community building:
551 integrating Terra Sigillata (Samian) research into the Wikidata community', *AeC*, vol.
552 34, no. 1, pp. 157–164, 2023, doi: 10.19282/ac.34.1.2023.17.
- 553 [3] N. Hartl, E. Wössner, and Y. Sure-Vetter, 'Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur
554 (NFDI)', *Informatik Spektrum*, vol. 44, no. 5, pp. 370–373, Oct. 2021, doi:
555 10.1007/s00287-021-01392-6.
- 556 [4] L. Rossenova et al., 'How are NFDI consortia using Knowledge Graphs? An overview
557 of common functions and challenges by the Working Group "Knowledge Graphs"', in
558 *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure 2025*, Y. Sure-Vetter
559 and G. Paul, Eds, Aachen: Squirrel Papers, Aug. 2025, p. 7(5), Q5. doi:
560 10.5281/zenodo.16736077.
- 561 [5] K. Fischer et al., 'Windows on Data: Federating Research Data with FAIR Digital
562 Objects and Linked Open Data', in *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data*
563 *Infrastructure 2025*, Y. Sure-Vetter and P. Groth, Eds, Aachen: Squirrel Papers, Aug.
564 2025, p. 7(5), Q3. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.16736221.
- 565 [6] F. Thiery et al., 'Object-Related Research Data Workflows Within NFDI4Objects and
566 Beyond', in *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure*, Y.
567 Sure-Vetter and C. Goble, Eds, Hannover: TIB Open Publishing, Sept. 2023, pp.
568 CoRDI2023-46. doi: 10.52825/cordi.v1i.326.
- 569 [7] S. C. Schmidt, F. Thiery, and M. Trognitz, 'Practices of Linked Open Data in
570 Archaeology and Their Realisation in Wikidata', *Digital*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 333–364,
571 June 2022, doi: 10.3390/digital2030019.

- 572 [8] F. Thiery and P. Thiery, 'Linked Open Ogham. How to publish and interlink various
573 Ogham Data?', *Archeologia e Calcolatori*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 105–114, 2023, doi:
574 10.19282/ac.34.1.2023.12.
- 575 [9] F. Thiery, L. Rossenova, D. Mietchen, T. Homburg, and P. Thiery, 'Distributed Research
576 Data Knowledge Graphs - Challenges of federated queries using the Wikiverse and
577 OpenStreetMap within the NFDI Knowledge Graph Ecosystem', in *Proceedings of the
578 Conference on Research Data Infrastructure 2025*, Y. Sure-Vetter and P. Groth, Eds,
579 Aachen: Squirrel Papers, Aug. 2025, p. 7(5), Q2. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.16736047.
- 580 [10] F. Thiery, L. Rossenova, and O. Simons, 'Wikibase instances in the Cultural Heritage
581 Domain: Examples from the German humanities NFDI consortia', *Squirrel Papers*, vol.
582 6, no. 4, p. #4, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14055699.
- 583 [11] F. Thiery and F. Schenk, 'Modelling of Uncertainty in Geo Sciences Sites', *Squirrel
584 Papers*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. #4, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10255259.
- 585 [12] P. Ó Dálaigh, 'The Holy Wells of County Kilkenny - Volume 2', Doctoral thesis, Mary
586 Immaculate College, University of Limerick, 2018. Accessed: Jan. 11, 2025. [Online].
587 Available: <https://dspace.mic.ul.ie/handle/10395/2584>
- 588 [13] S. C. Schmidt, F. Thiery, and M. Trognitz, 'Practices of Linked Open Data in
589 Archaeology and Their Realisation in Wikidata', *Digital*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 333–364,
590 June 2022, doi: 10.3390/digital2030019.
- 591 [14] F. Schenk, U. Hambach, S. Britzius, D. Veres, and F. Sirocko, 'A Cryptotephra Layer in
592 Sediments of an Infilled Maar Lake from the Eifel (Germany): First Evidence of
593 Campanian Ignimbrite Ash Airfall in Central Europe', *Quaternary*, vol. 7, no. 2, p. 17,
594 Mar. 2024, doi: 10.3390/quat7020017.
- 595 [15] T. Tsanova *et al.*, 'Upper Palaeolithic layers and Campanian Ignimbrite/Y-5 tephra in
596 Toplitsa cave, Northern Bulgaria', *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports*, vol. 37,
597 p. 102912, June 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jasrep.2021.102912.
- 598 [16] F. G. Fedele, B. Giaccio, R. Isaia, and G. Orsi, 'The Campanian Ignimbrite Eruption,
599 Heinrich Event 4, and palaeolithic change in Europe: A high-resolution investigation',
600 in *Geophysical Monograph Series*, vol. 139, A. Robock and C. Oppenheimer, Eds,
601 Washington, D. C.: American Geophysical Union, 2003, pp. 301–325. doi:
602 10.1029/139GM20.
- 603 [17] M. W. Morley and J. C. Woodward, 'The Campanian Ignimbrite (Y5) tephra at Crvena
604 Stijena Rockshelter, Montenegro', *Quat. res.*, vol. 75, no. 3, pp. 683–696, May 2011,
605 doi: 10.1016/j.yqres.2011.02.005.
- 606 [18] F. Thiery and F. Schenk, 'How to locate the Campanian Ignimbrite site Urluia based
607 on literature? How to provide and publish this data in a FAIR way?', *Squirrel Papers*,
608 vol. 5, no. 1, p. #5, 2023, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10262720.
- 609 [19] F. Thiery and F. Schenk, 'Campanian Ignimbrite Geo Locations', *Squirrel Papers*, vol. 5,
610 no. 2, p. #2, 2023, doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10361309.

